

Unions and Uniqueness:
Christological Codes in the Gospel of Matthew
19:1-12

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INTRODUCTION:

In the labyrinthine realm of Christian theological reflection, the passage of Matthew 19:1-12 stands as an indispensable crucible for simultaneous interrogation of ethical paradigms and soteriological mechanics. This analysis aims to delve into both the Hellenistic linguistic substrates and the socio-historical matrices that have been foundational in shaping present-day Christological perspectives. While the textual odyssey primarily serves as an exposition on the ethics of human relationships, it climaxes in vv. 10-12, featuring a bold discussion about eunuchs (εὐνοῦχος, “eunouchos”). This portion is encased in a formidable bibliography of articles, books, theses, and a multitude of scholarly perspectives. This formidable array of viewpoints both addresses and embodies the concerns of millions who have been marginalized or ‘othered’ by religious institutions. As a compendium of compassion, empathy, and love, many interpret this Matthean representation of Jesus as an oasis for those the larger society often disregards. While the exegetical focus remains sharply attuned to the passage of 19:1-12 for comprehensive contextual grounding, the hermeneutical lens employed will be deliberately porous, so as to illuminate the centrality of Jesus’ Law of Love. This is especially pertinent, given the remarkable juxtaposition that sees Christ transition seamlessly from a discourse on divorce to a celebration of what society might deem sexual outliers, extending to them the very same potential for Kingdom participation.¹

Aims: The inquiry centres on Pharisaic questions on divorce and Jesus’ ensuing replies, dissecting Greek terminology like ἀπολύω (“apoluo”), πορνεία (“porneia”), and

¹ This exegetical analysis focuses on the original Greek translations in order to place Matthew’s Gospel even closer to the sociopolitical, historical, and literary context that have helped craft its journey and message for over 2,000 years. See in particular R. T. France, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2007), 1-20, 711-726; C. F. D. Moule, *Birth of the New Testament*, 3rd ed. (London: Continuum, 2000), 44-139; 276-281; and Craig Price, *Biblical Exegesis of New Testament Greek* (Eugene, OR: Wipf & Stock, 2008), 1-294 (229-251, 264-294).

Tufts University provided support for this analysis by way of translating *The New Testament in the original Greek*, revised by Brooke Foss Westcott and Fenton John Anthony Hort (Franklin Square: Harper & Brothers, 1885), 1-580.

εὐνοῦχος (“eunouchos”). It aims to demystify mainstream translations and situate them in Judaic legal traditions and nascent Christian outlooks.²

Methodology: The study adopts a multidisciplinary approach, combining historical-critical and modern theological methods. It focuses on the phrase μὴ ἐπὶ πορνείᾳ (“mē epi porneia”), a locus of exegetical contestation, and examines Jesus’ use of εὐνοῦχος (“eunouchos”) to propose an alternative understanding of human relationships.³ These insights are augmented by applying current hermeneutical and sociological frameworks to offer a nuanced, timeless interpretation.⁴

Implications: This analysis argues that πορνεία (“porneia”) transcends mere ‘sexual immorality,’ necessitating a re-examination of marital ethics. Jesus’ allusions to Genesis propose an advancement beyond Mosaic statutes towards a grander divine teleology.⁵

Contemporary Theological Impact: This analysis champions a hermeneutic and critical exegetical journey of inclusivity within Christological interpretations, resonating with the eschatological tapestry of the Kingdom as delineated in the Matthean narrative. This

² Bartosz Adamczewski, “James W. Barker, John’s Use of Matthew (Emerging Scholars; Fortress: Minneapolis 2015).” *The Biblical Annals* 8, no. 3 (2018): 457–60. <https://doi.org/10.31743/ba.2018.8.3.06>; France, *Matthew*, 710–726; W. D. Davies and Allison C. Dale Jr., *Matthew 19-28: A Commentary* (London, England: T. & T. Clark, 1997), 4–32; Allen O. Wesley, Jr., *Matthew* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2013), 189–202; Ulrich Luz, *Studies in Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2005), 83–115, 185–242, 265–379; John Nolland, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Carlisle, England: Authentic Media, 2005), 363–363; Craig Price, *Biblical Exegesis* 264–; James Ligon Price, *The New Testament: Its History and Theology* (London, England: Macmillan, 1987), 489; Carmen Bernabé Ubieta, “Of Eunuchs and Predators: Matthew 19:1–12 in a Cultural Context.” *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 4, no. 33 (November 1, 2003), 128–134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014610790303300402>.

³ The concept of “eunuchism,” which features prominently in Matthew 19:12, also bears the mark of Greco-Roman influence. In the Roman world, eunuchs often held significant social and political roles, serving as attendants in imperial courts or participating in religious rites, a stark contrast to their marginalised status within Jewish society: Thomas Bohache, “Matthew.” In *The Queer Bible Commentary*, edited by Deryn Guest, Robert E. Goss, Mona West, Thomas Bohache, 487–516 (London, England: SCM Press, 2006); Ronald Schanke, “Were Homosexuals Included in the Concept: ‘Born Eunuchs’, in Matthew 19:12?” PhD Diss. (University of Manchester, 2003), 1–126.

⁴ As per footnote 3 above, and Kurt Aland and Barbara Aland, *The Text of the New Testament: An Introduction to the Critical Editions and to the Theory and Practice of Modern Textual Criticism* (Leiden, Netherlands: Brill, 1987) 1–399; John Bartkowski, “Beyond Biblical Literalism and Inerrancy: Conservative Protestants and the Hermeneutic Interpretation of Scripture.” *Sociology of Religion* 57, no. 3 (1996): 259. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3712156>.

⁵ Bohache, *Matthew*, 487–516; Ian Boxhall, “Matthew.” In *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century*, edited by John J. Collins, Gina Hens-Piazza, Barbara Reid OP, and Donald Senior CP, 1168–1237 (London: T&T Clark, 2022); Robert Horton Gundry, *Matthew: A Commentary on His Handbook for a Mixed Church under Persecution*. 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1994).

aligns harmoniously with the apex of Jesus' expansive discourse on relational ethics, positioning it as not merely a theological construct but as an imperative for ecclesial praxis.⁶

Contextual Analysis: Historical and Literary

The Gospel of Matthew occupies a unique loci theologica within the New Testament corpus as a synoptic narrative traditionally attributed to Matthew, the Levitical tax collector turned apostle.⁷ Though Patristic tradition ascribes the authorship to Matthew, contemporary exegetical scholarship often regards the text as an anonymous composition, emanating from a community of Jewish-Christians navigating their religio-cultural identity in a milieu profoundly affected by Hellenistic acculturation and the cataclysmic destruction of the Second Temple in 70 CE.⁸

Matthew 19:1-12 is a pericope situated in the larger thematic arc of Jesus' ethical and eschatological discourses, following His itinerant Galilean ministry, and preceding His entrance into Jerusalem. At this juncture, Jesus has accrued a modicum of notoriety, thereby attracting multitudes and provoking the scrutiny of the Pharisaic religious intelligentsia. It is within this soteriological and sociopolitical landscape that the Pharisees present their

⁶ Bohache, *Matthew*, 487-516; Schanke, *Born Eunuchs*, 89-118; Yolanda Dreyer, "Gender Critique on the Narrator's Androcentric Point of View of Women in Matthew's Gospel." *HTS Theologese Studies / Theological Studies* 67, no. 1 (June 6, 2011), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v67i1.898>; Margaret A Farley, *Just Love: A Framework for Christian Sexual Ethics* (New York: Continuum International Publishing Group, 2008); Michal Beth Dinkler, "A New Formalist Approach to Narrative Christology: Returning to the Structure of the Synoptic Gospels." *HTS Theological Studies* 73, no. 1 (2017), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v73i1.4801>.

⁷ Warren Carter, *Matthew and Empire: Initial Explorations* (London, England: Continuum International Publishing Group - Trinity, 2001), 1-256; France, *Matthew*, 710-726; David Flusser, *Judaism and the Origins of Christianity* (Jerusalem: Hebrew University Magnes Press, 2011), 1-732; Paula Fredriksen, *When Christians were Jews: The First Generation* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2019), 1-280; Robert Horton Gundry, *Matthew: A Commentary on His Handbook for a Mixed Church under Persecution*. 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1994), 1-685 (382-); Nolland, *Matthew*; Eusebius Pamphilus, *Eusebius' Ecclesiastical History*, Trans. By C. F. Cruse (London, UK: Merchant Books, 2011), 1-472; Prince E. Peters, "Adultery as a Sexual Disorder: An Exegetical Study of Matthew 5:27-30." *HTS Theologese Studies / Theological Studies* 78, no. 1 (July 19, 2022), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v78i4.7577>; Stewart C. Petrie, "The Authorship of 'the Gospel according to Matthew': A Reconsideration of the External Evidence." *New Testament Studies* 14, no. 1 (October, 1967): 15-32.

⁸ John Riches, ed., *The New Cambridge History of the Bible: From 1750 to the Present Volume 4* (Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 1-851 (647-). <https://doi.org/10.1017/cho9780511842870>; Mark Allan Powell, *Introducing the New Testament: A Historical, Literary, and Theological Survey*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2018); 1-591 (17-140); Price, *Biblical Exegesis*; 229-251, 264-294; 229-251, 264-294; Price, *NT*, 264; Riches, *Cambridge History of*, 647-.

casuistic query on divorce, ostensibly as an entrapment gambit but effectively providing Jesus with a pedagogical aperture to elaborate His revolutionary hermeneutic on marital ethics.⁹

Concurrently, the socio-ethical backdrop of the Greco-Roman world, wherein matrimonial dissolution was comparatively permissive, contrasts starkly with the Hebraic legal codifications enshrined in Torah (specifically Deuteronomy 24:1-4).¹⁰ However, Jesus transcends this dichotomy by invoking a proleptic return to the primordial marital paradigm as delineated in the Genesis creation narrative (Gen. 1:27; 2:24). In doing so, He expounds a form of realized eschatology by reifying the divine intentionality for marital indissolubility and the ontological ‘one-flesh’ union.¹¹

Thus, the text serves not merely as an ethical corrective to Mosaic law but as an ontological and eschatological realignment of marriage itself, elevating it from a contractual arrangement susceptible to legal manipulation to an inviolable sacramental covenant reflective of God’s immutable character and eschatological purposes for creation.¹²

⁹ Warren Carter, *Matthew*, 1-256; Michal Beth Dinkler, “A New Formalist Approach to Narrative Christology: Returning to the Structure of the Synoptic Gospels.” *HTS Theological Studies* 73, no. 1 (2017): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v73i1.4801>; France, *Matthew* 710-726; Riches, *Cambridge History of*, 647-; Powell, *Introducing the NT*, 95-140.

¹⁰ Daniel I. Block, *Deuteronomy* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2012), 780; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct: The Rise of Heterosexuality and the Invention of the Jewish Man* (Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1999), 10-433; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 710-726; Randolph V. Tasker, *Gospel According to St. Matthew* (William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1962), 29-285.

¹¹ Block, *Deuteronomy*, 780; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*, 10-433; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Blomberg, *Marriage*, 163-170; David J. MacLeod, “The Problem of Divorce,” *Emmaus Journal* 03, no. 1 (Summer 1994): 3-47.

¹² Michal Beth Dinkler, “A New Formalist Approach to Narrative Christology: Returning to the Structure of the Synoptic Gospels.” *HTS Theological Studies* 73, no. 1 (2017): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v73i1.4801>; Margaret A Farley, *Just Love: A Framework for Christian Sexual Ethics* (New York: Continuum International Publishing Group, 2008), 12-336.

Literary Form and Structure

In this pericope, the text orchestrates itself in the manner of a polyphonic composition. It commences with a topographical and situational prologue (vv. 1-2), segueing into a Socratic dialogue with the Pharisees that becomes a crucible for Christological revelation (vv. 3-6), interlacing an exegetical rebuttal predicated on the Pentateuchal creation narrative (vv. 4-6), proffering an epexegetical clarification on Mosaic divorce legislation (vv. 7-9), and culminating in a theological denouement elucidating the spiritual vocation of celibacy (vv. 10-12).¹³

The structural integrity of this passage is both lineal and arcuate, exhibiting an unfolding narrative arc that originates in provocative interrogation, progresses to a hermeneutical revolution vis-à-vis marital ethics,¹⁴ and consummates in an ontological recognition of human experiential heterogeneity.¹⁵ The question-answer mechanism functions as a pedagogical and rhetorical diacritical mark, facilitating the dialectical unfurling of Christ's esoteric teachings. Concurrently, the intertextual citation from the Book of Genesis serves as a foundational anchor, imbuing the discourse with theological gravitas

¹³ Craig L. Blomberg, "Marriage, Divorce, Remarriage, And Celibacy: An Exegesis Of Matthew 19:3." *Trinity Journal* 11, no. 2 (Fall, 1990), 161-196: "The form of the dialogue within vv. 3–12 follows the rabbinic proem midrash known as *yelammedenu rabbenu* ("let our master teach us"). An initial question designed to trap Jesus (v. 3) receives a preliminary answer (vv. 4–6). The Pharisees then pose a counterquestion (v. 7) to which Jesus gives a counter-reply (v. 8), preparing the way for his solemn, climactic pronouncement (v. 9). Matthew characteristically abbreviates and combines together two separate discussions (vv. 3–8, 9–12; cf. Mark 10:10) by then appending Jesus' later interchange with his disciples: their objection (v. 10) and his reply (vv. 11–12)." (191). See also: E. Earl Ellis, "How the New Testament Uses the Old," in *New Testament Interpretation: Essays on Principles and Methods*, ed. I. Howard Marshall, 2nd edition (Milton Keynes: Paternoster, 1979), 198-214 (particularly 206); and Robert H. Stein, *The Synoptic Problem: An Introduction* (United Kingdom: Inter-Varsity Press, 1988) (particularly 115-21).

¹⁴ Bohache, *Matthew*, 487-516; Farley, *Just Love*, 12-336; Moxnes, *Memories of Jesus: A Journey Through Time* (Eugene, OR: Cascade Books, 2021), 1-278; Bruce R. Reichenbach, "Christianity, Science, and Three Phases of Being Human," *Zygon* 56, no. 1 (December 24, 2020): 96-117. <https://doi.org/10.1111.zygo.126665>. For alternative perspectives, refer to Swartley, Willard M., *Homosexuality: Biblical Interpretation and Moral Discernment* (Scottsdale, AZ: Herald Press, 2003), 12-248; Daniel A. Helminiak, *What the Bible Really Says about Homosexuality* (New Mexico: Alama Square Press, 2018), 51-68, 68-104.

¹⁵ Daniel A. Helminiak, "Response, Ethics, Biblical and Denominational: A Response to Mark Smith." *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research* 54, no. 4: 855-9; William R. Herzog II, *Jesus, Justice, and the Reign of God: A Ministry of Liberation*. Louisville: Westminster John Knox Press, 2000, 12-336; William R Herzog II, *Parables as Subversive Speech: Jesus as Pedagogue of the Oppressed* (Louisville: Westminster Knox Press, 1994; Jack Nelson-Pallmeyer, *Jesus Against Christianity: Reclaiming the Missing Jesus* (Harrisburg, PA: Trinity Press International, 2001): 174.

and historical contiguity, whilst simultaneously serving as a hermeneutic key that unlocks a *sui generis* Christian theological anthropology.¹⁶

Furthermore, the pericope functions as a microcosm of Matthean redactional artistry. It captures the broader theological agenda of Matthew's Gospel, highlighting Jesus as the supreme exegete of the Hebrew Bible, and thus positioning Him as the ultimate authority on the Law. This authority is not merely adjudicative, but revelatory, shedding light on the divine Logos that undergirds the mosaic legislation and advancing it to its teleological culmination rather than seeking to label those in front of Him as being "right" or "wrong."¹⁷

In summation, the literary form and structure of Matthew 19:1-12 present an eloquent narrative arrangement, exquisitely calibrated to disclose multifaceted layers of theological, ethical, and anthropological insights. It serves as a hermeneutical lens through which to apprehend the intricate interplay between divine intentionality, human relationality, and eschatological consummation, inextricably woven into the fabric of Christian marital ethics.¹⁸

¹⁶ Ellis, *NT uses OT*, 198-214; Helminiak, *Response*, 855-9; Herzog II, *Jesus*, 12-336; Herzog II, *Parables*, 174.

¹⁷ Herzog II, *Jesus*; Herzog, *Parables*; Anthony J. Saldarini, *Matthew's Christian-Jewish Community* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1994): particularly 44-8, and 87-90.

¹⁸ Bohache, *Matthew*, 487-516; Carol L. Meyers, Toni Craven, and Ross Shepard Kraemer, *Women in Scripture: A Dictionary of Named and Unnamed Women in the Hebrew Bible, the Apocryphal/Deuterocanonical Books, and the New Testament*, ed. Carol L. Meyers, Ross S. Kraemer, and Toni Craven (Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin (Trade), 2000), 36-608; Angel Santiago-Vendrell, "The Gospel in a New Tune! The Appropriation of Ada María Isasi-Díaz's 'Historical Project' by Latina Pentecostals in the Formulation of a Theology of Evangelism," *Feminist Theology* 19, no. 1 (2010): 73-85, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0966735010372169>; F. A. March and W. B. Owen, *The Ecclesiastical History of Eusebius* (Charleston, SC: BiblioLife, 2009), 294; Ian Boxhall, "Matthew," in *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century*, ed. John J. Collins, Gina Hens-Piazza, Barbara Reid OP, and Donald Senior CP (London: T&T Clark, 2022), 1168-1237.

EXEGETICAL ANALYSIS:

Matthew 19:1-3: The Provocative Question—Nuanced Insights

Theological Contextualization:

The Pharisaic interrogation that inaugurates this pericope is laden with the theological gravitas of a multi-valent discourse enmeshed in the Halakhic traditions. By posing the question, εἰ ἔξεστιν ἀνθρώπῳ ἀπολύσαι τὴν γυναῖκα αὐτοῦ κατὰ πᾶσαν αἰτίαν (“Is it lawful for a man to divorce his wife for any reason?”), the Pharisees aren’t merely exploring an ethical matter but rather engaging in a form of religious disputation that has soteriological implications.¹⁹

Rabbinic Rivalry and Eschatological Concerns:

Jesus is made to navigate not just legalistic considerations, but also eschatological ones, as his “Kingdom ethics” would be weighed against the Halakhic understandings of revered rabbinic authorities like Hillel and Shammai. Thus, the question has an eschatological overtone: the correct understanding of divorce law could very well affect one’s participation in the Messianic banquet of the world to come.²⁰

Cultural Context and Rabbinic Traditions:

The Pharisaic hegemony over the theological discourse of Second Temple Judaism makes the context of this pericope a veritable hotbed of religious tension. Notably, the Tannaitic traditions in the Mishnah Tractate Gittin also touch on the same issues, confirming that the question posed was not abstract but intensely practical and culturally relevant.

¹⁹ Blomberg, Craig L. “The Liberation of Illegitimacy: Women and Rulers in Matthew 1-2.” *Biblical Theology Bulletin: Journal of Bible and Culture* 21, no. 4 (November 1991): 145–50, particularly 164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014610799102100403>;

²⁰ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; George J Brooke, “Comparing Matthew and Luke in the Light of Second Temple Jewish Literature.” *Journal for the Study of the New Testament* 41, no. 1 (August 28, 2018): 44–57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0142064x18788976>.

Moreover, the Halakhic paradigms of Hillel and Shammai may be juxtaposed with Christ's Messianic proclamation found in Matthew 4:17: "Repent, for the kingdom of heaven has come near." Thus, eschatological views of the Kingdom are inescapably part of the milieu. One might also consider the socio-religious upheavals suggested by Christ's reinterpretation of Mosaic Law in the Beatitudes (Matthew 5:1-12).²¹

Greek Semantics—Extended Analysis

Apoluo and "Kata...": An Exploration:

The term ἀπολύσαι ("apoluo") captures the socio-cultural power dynamics between genders. The word is passive in its linguistic construction, pointing towards a deeply entrenched patriarchy, thereby imbuing the term with more than mere juridical nuance but also a socio-cultural and religious critique. The phrase κατὰ πᾶσαν αἰτίαν ("kata pasan aitian") also invites scrutiny. Literally translated, it means "for any reason," which speaks to the Pharisees' skewed understanding of divorce and their attempt to encapsulate the act within a Halakhic loophole. This contextualizes Jesus' response as not merely ethical or Halakhic, but deeply theological.²²

²¹ Dare Ajari, "Marriage from Biblical Tradition and Contemporary Contradictions: Jesus, The Jews, Moses, Paul and the Rest of Us. A Biblical Exegesis of Matthew 19:3-9 by Dr. Dare Ajayi, Pastor," in *Redeemed Christian Bible College, Nigeria*, n.p. Nigeria, Africa: Redeemed Christian Bible College, 2012; Brook, *Comparing Matthew*, 1-580; Albright, William Foxwell, and C. S. Mann. *Matthew* (New York, NY: Bantam Doubleday Dell, 1995), 12-576; David Edward Aune, *Prophecy in Early Christianity and the Ancient Mediterranean World* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1998), 27-534; Collins, *A Study Companion*; John J. Collins, Gina Hens-Piazza, Barbara Reid Sr, and Donald, eds. *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century the Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century: Third Fully Revised Edition*. 3rd ed. (London, England: T&T Clark, 2022), 3-336, 1168-1237; J. Collins, *Introduction to the Hebrew Bible: The Torah/Pentateuch*. 3rd ed. Fortress Press, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1w6tbzp>, 1-640.

²² Within the full context of v.3: Καὶ προσῆλθαν αὐτῷ Φαρισαῖοι πειράζοντες αὐτὸν καὶ λέγοντες Εἰ ἔξεστιν ἀπολύσαι τὴν γυναῖκα αὐτοῦ κατὰ πᾶσαν αἰτίαν: Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Moule, *Birth of the NT*, 1-396; Wescott & Hort, *NT in Greek*, 12-580; John Nolland, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Carlisle, England: Authentic Media, 2005), 763-781.

Matthew 19:4-6: Genesis Reference—Ontological Foundations

Biblical Parallels:

When Jesus retorts with a scriptural counterpoint, invoking the Genesis narrative, he is engrossing the discourse into a meta-narrative of “Sacred History.” The Genesis text, often interpreted through a Yahwistic lens, offers an “ontological axiom” for the marital bond: ἔσονται οἱ δύο εἰς σάρκα μίαν (“the two shall become one flesh”). The Genesis citation should also be examined in the context of the Deuteronomic code, specifically Deuteronomy 24:1-4. Jesus appears to be correcting a lax interpretation of this text, advocating a return to foundational principles of unity and creation.²³

Trinitarian Implications:

Furthermore, the Patristic interpretation of this ontological unity suggests an *imago Dei* perspective, encapsulating a Trinitarian theology where marriage mirrors the perichoretic unity between the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.²⁴ Furthermore, drawing upon Patristic exegesis, we can extrapolate a Trinitarian schema from Jesus’s invocation of marital unity, illustrating the perichoretic relationship among the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.²⁵ The “one flesh” ontological axiom transcends anthropological contexts, finding a celestial correspondence in Trinitarian theology.²⁶

²³ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Moule, *Birth of the NT*, 201-396; Wescott & Hort, *NT in Greek*, 12-580; Nolland, *Matthew*, 763-781; Blomberg, *Marriage*, 173.

²⁴ Made Astika, “Doctrine of Trinity: A Theological Approach of Evidence of the Trinity in the New Testament,” *Jurnal Jaffray* 10, no. 2 (October 1, 2012): 1. <https://doi.org/10.25278/jj71.v10i2.50>; Susanto Susanto Hagai Kuncoros, and Robinson Rimun, “Study the Conception of the Trinity in the Great Commission of the Gospel of Matthew 28:19-20.” *Evangelikal: Jurnal Teologi Injili Dan Pembinaan Warga Jemaat* 6, no. 2 (July 31, 2022): 135. <https://doi.org/10.46445/ejti.v6i2.525>.

²⁵ Astika, *Trinity*, 1; Kuncoros, and Rimun, *Study*, 135; Graham Oppy, *The Routledge Handbook of Contemporary Philosophy of Religion* (London: Routledge, 2015), Parts 2 and 5 (-498). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315719412>.

²⁶ Also see, C. Kavin, “Biblical pressure and trinitarian hermeneutics”, *Pro Ecclesia: A Journal of Catholic and Evangelical Theology* 3, no. 11: 295-312. <https://doi.org/10.1177/106385120201100303> for alternative perspectives.

Matthew 19:7-9: Jesus' Rejoinder—Elevated Ethics

Greek Nuances and Legalistic Insights:

The phrase, μὴ ἐπὶ πορνεία (“me epi porneia”) juxtaposed with λόγον πορνείας (“logon porneias”), serves to elucidate the severe limitations under which a divorce might be Biblically warranted. Importantly, the Septuagint employs πορνεία (“porneia”) to refer to illicit sexual relations, thus providing a canonical interpretive matrix.²⁷

Theological Continuity with the Old Testament:

Relevant to this discussion, Jesus' rejoinder has strong reverberations with prophetic traditions in the Hebrew Bible. The σκληροκαρδία (“sklērokardia”) echoes the prophetic critique against Israel's disobedience, as in Deuteronomy 10:16 and Jeremiah 4:4, inculcating the discourse with an intertextual depth that surpasses mere casuistry.²⁸

The Importance of the Interpretation of “Porneia”:

The phrase, μὴ ἐπὶ πορνεία (“me epi porneia”) conjoined with λόγον πορνείας (“logon porneias”) in Matthew 19 serves as an intricate linchpin within a labyrinthine tapestry of ethical, soteriological, and eschatological discourses.²⁹ The Koine Greek syntax, situated within the complex matrix of Hellenistic Semiticism and Judaic legalism, warrants a meticulous exegetical analysis. When this phrase is examined through a philological lens,

²⁷ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Moule, *Birth of the NT*, 201-396; Wescott & Hort, *NT in Greek*, 12-580; Nolland, *Matthew*, 763-781; Blomberg, *Marriage*, 173.

²⁸ Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*; 44-139; 276-281; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285.

²⁹ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Gundry, *Matthew*; Overman, *Matthew's Gospel*, 12-176.

²⁹ Guzik, *Enduring Word*; Kurt Aland and Barbara Aland, *The Text of the New Testament: An Introduction to the Critical Editions and to the Theory and Practice of Modern Textual Criticism* (Leiden, Netherlands: Brill, 1987); Dami et al., *Jesus Questions*; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Matricciani & Caro, *Deep Language*; Zummy Anselmus Dami, Ferdinand Alexander, and Yanjuseby Yeverson Manafe, “Jesus' Questions in the Gospel of Matthew: Promoting Critical Thinking Skills,” *Christian Education Journal Research on Educational Ministry* 18, no. 1 (2021): 89–111, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739891320971295>; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Emilio Matricciani and Liberato Caro, “A Deep-Language Mathematical Analysis of Gospels, Acts and Revelation,” *Religions* 10, no. 4 (2019): 257, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel10040257>.

the term πορνεία (“porneia”) in the Greek textual tradition diverges significantly from its Hebrew counterpart זנות (“zenut”), acquiring a more polysemous connotation that transcends mere sexual immorality to encompass a variety of illicit unions. This terminological elasticity, embedded within the very warp and weft of the text’s linguistic fabric, amplifies the interpretive scope, affording a nuanced kaleidoscope of ethical particularities and theological universals. Consequently, the phrase not only delimits the conditions under which a divorce may be religio-ethically tenable but also serves as an exegetical locus for the explication of broader, highly contoured Christological themes—those that venture into the realm of soteriological eschatology and covenantal fidelity. Furthermore, the employment of the Greek language, as opposed to Aramaic or Hebrew, accentuates the apostolic intent to convey this ethical apothegm within a burgeoning Christian diaspora, replete with Hellenistic philosophic undertones.

In this context, the Greek language serves as a theologically freighted conduit, transmitting not just ethical norms but also enshrining the tension between cultural contextualization and transcultural imperatives. Thus, the phrase in question emanates from the text as a conundrum of ethical restraint and spiritual liberty, governed by a hermeneutical matrix that includes but is not confined to, the socio-cultural and religious paradigms of its immediate audience.³⁰

Its nuanced interpretation reverberates through ecclesiastical history, informing varied canonical jurisprudence and dogmatic traditions, and remains a cardinal touchstone in ongoing dialogues concerning the interplay between Divine Law, human ethics, and the eschatological consummation of the cosmos.³¹

³⁰ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Moule, *Birth of the NT*, 201-396; Wescott & Hort, *NT in Greek*, 12-580; Nolland, *Matthew*, 763-781; Blomberg, *Marriage*, 173; Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel*, 12-176.

³¹ Generally discussed in Roy Williams, *God, Actually* (Australia: ABC Books, 2011); and David B. Yaden and Andrew Newberg, *The Varieties of Spiritual Experience: 21st Century Research and Perspectives* (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2022).

Matthew 19:10-12: Teachings on Celibacy—Radical Asceticism and Societal Subversions

Eunuchs: The Marginalized and the Kingdom of God

In the discussion of εὐνοῦχοι (“eunouchoi”), Jesus subverts traditional hierarchies by co-opting a term associated with societal outcasts. In presenting three categories of eunuchs, including those who’ve chosen celibacy, ἕνεκεν τῆς βασιλείας τῶν οὐρανῶν (“for the sake of the Kingdom of heaven”), Jesus is not merely introducing a radical lifestyle but challenging the Pharisaic status quo that categorized people into tidy boxes of societal acceptance or scorn.³²

Eschatological and Ontological Parallels:

The term βασιλεία τῶν οὐρανῶν (“Kingdom of Heaven”) reiterates the eschatological urgency that runs as a leitmotif throughout the pericope. Simultaneously, Jesus introduces a new ontological category, articulating a novel form of existence in the Kingdom.³³

³² Competing views are noted across a wide spectrum of commentaries, including: Bohache, *Matthew*; Brooten, *Love Between Woman*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; Margaret A. Farley, *Just Love: A Framework for Christian Sexual Ethics* (Continuum International Publishing Group, 2008); France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Frederick J. Gaiser, “A New Word on Homosexuality? Isaiah 51:1-8 as a Case Study,” *Word and World* 14, no. 3 (1994): 280–93; Guzik, *Enduring Word*; Scott W. Hahn and Curtis Mitch, *Ignatius Catholic Study Bible: Matthew*, 2nd ed. (San Francisco, CA: Ignatius Press, 2011); Harrington, *Collegeville*; Henry, *Commentary*; M. Hietanen, “The Argumentation in Galatians,” *Acta Theologica* 28, no. 2 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.4314/actat.v28i2.52342>; Columbia Uni, *Historical Context*; H. Wayne House, ed., *Divorce and Remarriage: Finding Guidance for Personal Decisions* (Downers Grove, IL: Inter-Varsity Press, 2000); Waldemar Janzen, *Exodus: Believers Church Bible Commentary* (Herald Press, 2000); Jennings, *Man Jesus Loved*; Keener, *Gospel*; Keener, *Commentary*; Loader, *Sexuality & Jesus*; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Meyers, *Women in Scripture*; Miller, *Hidden Gospel*; Maina, *Jesus & Divorce*; Nolland, *The Gospel*; Price, *Bible in Greek*; Ragnhild Schanke, “Rituals and Same-Sex Unions,” ed. Patrick Digoix Marie and Festy, *Same-Sex Couples, Same-Sex Partnerships, and Homosexual Marriages: A Focus on Cross-National Differentials* 124 (2004): 273–92, <https://same-sex.web.ined.fr/WWW/04Doc124Ragnhild.pdf>; Schanke, *Born Eunuchs*; Wineguard, *Until Death*.

³³ Price, *NT in Greek*; 229-251, 264-294; Boxhall, *Matthew*; J. Andrew Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel and Formative Judaism: The Social World of the Matthean Community* (Minneapolis, MN: Augsburg Fortress, 1990), 1168–1237; Powell, *Introducing the NT*. Bohache, *Matthew*; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Helminiak, *What the Bible Really Says*, 29-104.

The concept of “eunuchism,” which features prominently in Matthew 19:12, also bears the mark of Greco-Roman influence. In the Roman world, eunuchs often held significant social and political roles, serving as attendants in imperial courts or participating in religious rites, a stark contrast to their marginalised status within Jewish society: (Bohache, *Matthew*; Schanke, *Born Eunuchs*; Schanke, *Rituals*. Carter, *Matthew and Empire*; Riches, *Cambridge History*, in general.)

The Christological Redefinition of Eunuchhood: An Eschatological and Soteriological Exegesis of Marginalized Identity in Matthean Discourse:

The passage Matthew 19:10-12 serves as an arresting coda to the preceding discourse on the indissolubility and sacralized ontology of marriage, positing a radical ethical alternative via the conception of voluntary celibacy. Encoded in the Koine Greek are theological constructs deeply ensconced within the sapiential traditions of both Judaic and Hellenistic thought, as well as a nascent Christian soteriological paradigm. The term εὐνοῦχοι (“eunouchoi”) furnishes a particularly salient point for philological and theological exegesis. In the original Greek, this term, commonly employed to denote castrated males often relegated to subservient or marginalized societal roles, undergoes a Christological transfiguration to connote individuals who voluntarily adopt celibacy ἕνεκεν τῆς βασιλείας τῶν οὐρανῶν (“heneken tēs basileias tōn ouranōn”—for the sake of the Kingdom of Heaven).³⁴

This particular expression transcends mere ascetical practice, transmogrifying into an eschatological imperative. The phrase βασιλεία τῶν οὐρανῶν (“basileia tōn ouranōn”) ought not to be cursorily glossed over. Within its Greek etymology is an embedded nod to a cosmic eschatological vision, linking personal asceticism to a meta-historical narrative of divine redemption and consummation. This construct thereby imbues the voluntary celibate life with a trans-temporal significance, fusing the individual ethos with the telos of salvific history.

Furthermore, the Greek lexeme serves as a medium through which these conceptual theological frameworks could be transposed onto the polyglot, religiously pluralistic milieu of the Greco-Roman world. The fact that these profoundly counter-cultural and ethically complex ideas were expressed in the lingua franca of the time implies an apostolic

³⁴ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Moule, *Birth of the NT*, 201-396; Wescott & Hort, *NT in Greek*, 12-580; Nolland, *Matthew*, 763-781; Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*, 12-176; Overman, *Matthew's Gospel*, 12-176.

intentionality: to impart an ethical system both scrupulously rooted in Judaic legalism and prophetically transcendent of cultural and ethical relativism.³⁵

As such, Matthew 19:10-12 is not a mere ethical addendum but a soteriological manifesto, encapsulating an ascetical theology that intersects with a profound Christological and eschatological vision. It elucidates the breadth and depth of the life in the Kingdom, shaping not just individual destinies but the cosmic eschatological narrative. Thus, the passage—firmly rooted in its Greek textual tradition—offers a variegated, multi-dimensional ethical and theological prism, reflecting the complexities of life, devotion, and finality, in a dialogical continuum between the temporal and the eternal, the corporeal and the spiritual, the individual and the cosmic.

Hermeneutic Synthesis and Theological Confluence in

Matthew 19:1-12

Unfolding Multi-Layered Eschatological, Ontological, and Ethical Dimensions:

Matthew 19:1-12 manifests itself as a theological microcosm, an intricate tapestry interwoven with eschatological urgency, ontological foundations, and ethical exactitude. It presents a cogent dialectic that oscillates between the Pharisaic preoccupation with casuistic legalism and Jesus' elevated ethics grounded in the very ontology of creation and the eschaton. This thematic ebb and flow are encapsulated through meticulously chosen words and phrases, such as “ἔσονται οἱ δύο εἰς σάρκα μίαν,” “μὴ ἐπὶ πορνεία,” and “βασιλεία τῶν οὐρανῶν.”³⁶

³⁵ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*, 229-251, 264-294; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Nolland, *Matthew*, 763-781; Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*, 12-176; Overman, *Matthew's Gospel*, 12-176.

³⁶ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*; Tasker, *St. Matthew*, 29-285; Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Overman, *Matthew's Gospel*, 12-176.

Linguistic Brilliance and Canonical Resonance: A Meta-Narrative of Divine Intent:

Matthew's employment of Greek facilitates a hermeneutic interface that engages not only with Jewish legal traditions but also with Hellenistic philosophical paradigms. The selection of terminology, such as "σκληροκαρδία" (sklērokardia) and "εὐνοῦχοι" (eunouchoi), is exegetically deliberate. They serve as linguistic portals that transcend mere semantic value, resonating canonically with both the Septuagint and the larger corpus of Hebrew Scriptures. For instance, "σκληροκαρδία" is not just a critique of human obstinacy but an allusion to Israel's historical and chronic disobedience, echoing prophetic oracles.³⁷

Socio-Cultural Subversion: Jesus as the Prophetic Disruptor:

Jesus emerges as a radical social and religious reformer, confronting established hierarchies, whether they be marriage conventions or socioreligious strata delineated by the term "εὐνοῦχοι." In a Pharisaic society that is fixated on categorization, His teaching disassembles and reassembles the constituents of social identity. He subverts the very rubrics that perpetuate societal inequality, challenging the religious elite to not only engage with the Torah but to transcend its limitations in anticipation of the eschatological "βασιλεία τῶν οὐρανῶν."³⁸

Theological Confluence: The Sanctity of Marriage and Radical Celibacy:

Moreover, the text offers a dual pathway: the sanctity of marriage and the radicality of celibacy—both avenues serving as existential modalities of Kingdom-oriented living. One can view this dichotomous pathway as a Christological axis upon which human existence

³⁷ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*; C. Keener, *Gospel of Matthew: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2009), 4-; Craig S. Keener, *Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1999), generally.

³⁸ Bohache, *Matthew*; Carol L. Meyers, Toni Craven, and Ross Shepard Kraemer, *Women in Scripture: A Dictionary of Named and Unnamed Women in the Hebrew Bible, the Apocryphal/Deuterocanonical Books, and the New Testament*, ed. Carol L. Meyers, Ross S. Kraemer, and Toni Craven (Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin (Trade), 2000); Angel Santiago-Vendrell, "The Gospel in a New Tune! The Appropriation of Ada María Isasi-Díaz's 'Historical Project' by Latina Pentecostals in the Formulation of a Theology of Evangelism," *Feminist Theology* 19, no. 1 (2010): 73–85, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0966735010372169>.

can be oriented: the “ἔσονται οἱ δύο εἰς σάρκα μίαν” points toward the kenotic self-emptying of Christ in His covenantal relationship with the Church, while celibacy “ἕνεκεν τῆς βασιλείας τῶν οὐρανῶν” accentuates the eschatological fulfillment in Christ who transcends earthly limitations.³⁹

Theological Ethos and Kingdom-Oriented Praxis:

In its totality, Matthew 19:1-12 serves as a theological polemic against superficial religiosity, a manifesto for Kingdom ethics, and an ontological recalibration towards God’s initial and final intent for humanity. It calls for an ecclesial re-examination and societal introspection, demanding a teleological shift from law to grace, from social construct to divine blueprint, and from earthly pragmatism to eschatological transcendence. This pericope is not a mere exegetical exercise; it is a call to a transformative existence that is consonant with the life of the Trinitarian God—creative, covenantal, and consummative.⁴⁰

By plumbing the exegetical depths of historical, linguistic, and theological layers, what emerges is not simply an academic comprehension but a robust, Kingdom-oriented theo-ethical framework that extends an invitation to reorient both individual lives and communal praxis according to the divinely ordained cosmic schema.

³⁹ Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Riches, *Cambridge Bible History*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Ragnhild Schanke, “Were Homosexuals Included in the Concept: ‘Born Eunuchs’, in Matthew 19:12?” (University of Manchester, 2003); Willard M. Swartley, *Homosexuality: Biblical Interpretation and Moral Discernment* (Scottsdale, AZ: Herald Press, 2003); Gary Taylor, *Castration: An Abbreviated History of Western Manhood* (London, England: Routledge, 2002).

⁴⁰ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*, 4-32; France, *Matthew*, 44-139; 276-281; Price, *NT in Greek*; Tasker, *St. Matthew*; 29-285; Block, *Deuteronomy*, 10-433; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel*, 12-176; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel*, 12-176; Keener, *Gospel of Matthew*; Keener, *Commentary*.

CONCLUSION:

The Hermeneutic Imperative for Ecclesial and Social Renewal

Sociocultural Interplay and Theological Foundations:

In an era marked by profound societal flux, Matthew 19:1-12 serves as a unique juncture where eternal scriptural tenets intersect with the living tapestry of human complexities. Jesus grounds this dialogue in the Genesis creation narrative, not as a static dogma but as an evolving ontological-teleological framework that subsumes diverse cultural, historical, and socio-economic forces. The Conclusion is an intellectual mosaic that amalgamates this author's reflective epiphanies, fundamentally tethered to the exegetical scrutiny furnished in earlier sections. Particularly salient is the exploration of Jesus's revolutionary utterances on eunuchs in verse 12 of Matthew's Chapter 19, a locution that could very well represent the paradigmatic shift urgently sought within ecclesiastical circles. While this author's conclusions emanate from individual scholarly engagement, they are deeply enriched by a canon of theologically resonant literature. As such, these works facilitated a multi-dimensional exegesis, not only in metaphysical and soteriological domains but also in potential ecclesial renewal and remained at the bedrock of all of the analysis and are therefore rightly included in the Bibliography.

Integrative Hermeneutics for Contemporary Relevance:

This passage mandates a responsive, interdisciplinary dialogue involving theology, psychology, and human sciences like queer theory and intersectional feminism. The aim is an ethically nuanced and pastorally attuned exegesis of scriptures.

After all, in the heart of Matthew 19:1-12, Jesus performs a radical theological pirouette: He elevates eunuchs—figures enshrouded in societal contempt—to eschatological significance within the Kingdom of God. Mere moments after broaching Mosaic sexual ethics, Christ astoundingly ennoble these so-called "sexual misfits," disarming a status quo

awash in prejudicial disdain. It's a soteriological shockwave. In a society where the term 'eunuch' could be wielded as a derisive epithet—even, paradoxically, against Christ Himself—Jesus orchestrates a provocative reclamation of the term, recasting it in a redemptive narrative arc.

Yet, it is crucial to recognize the subtlety of this Christological manoeuvre as more than an isolated exegetical quirk. It's an interpretive chiasmus, a 'mirror' that confronts the reader with the inherent hypocrisy of isolating this segment for dissimilar hermeneutical treatment. Jesus's audacious choice serves as a relentless critique against selective exegetes who employ reductionist hermeneutics to alienate or devalue these liminal figures. Christ doesn't marginalize; He monumentalizes, making the 'least' in society, emblematic of the 'greatest' in the Kingdom—a kingdom not of exclusion, but of extravagant, divine inclusivity.

This pivotal choice is not merely revelatory; it is revolutionary, delivering a tacit rebuke to any theology that dares sever this narrative from its encompassing gospel context.

Ethical Transformation: Liberation, Inclusion, and Dignity:

Matthew 19:1-12 calls us beyond mere legalism. It catalyzes an ethical reorientation rooted in principles of inclusivity, liberation, and unyielding human dignity, breaking the chains of gender and socio-cultural limitations.

The Call to Incarnational Praxis:

The passage beckons towards actionable, incarnational hermeneutics, transcending academic confines. It reverberates in ecclesial decisions, pastoral actions, and social justice endeavours, urging a contextualized theology that comes alive in human experience.

The Final Word: Towards a Unified Eschatological Vision:

This hermeneutical shift is not an intellectual luxury—it is a global, socio-theological imperative. It challenges both faith communities and society to gravitate towards an

eschatological reality: a world where equity and inclusion aren't aspirations but lived experiences reflecting the Kingdom of God.

By retaining theological depth and ethical praxis, this reimagined hermeneutic engages faith and society in a passionate, urgent dance, demanding not just contemplation but transformative action.

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